

Game-based learning in a Production Engineering course in Brazil

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5096755>

Abstract

Production Management courses are key points in Production Engineering programs. Teaching concepts of Lean Manufacturing and Theory of Constraints (TOC) is an arduous task, since it involves the need to establish several important fundamentals. Traditional classes based on blackboard and speech tend to bring monotony and lack of interest to students, reducing their retention of content. On the other hand, there are active teaching methodologies that allow these concepts to be better worked and fixed. Among these methodologies is the Game-Based Learning (GBL). Based on the use of games for educational purposes, GBL allows simulate some scenarios and teach concepts, while take decisions. For about ten years, Production Management (III and IV) classes at the researched institution have been held with the support of different games: the "Beer Game" and the "Lean Board Game", in physical format and "Goldratt Simulator", a virtual simulator. Although the teacher of the subjects understands the importance of using games to complement the classes and understanding the concepts covered, this application had not been the target of previous researches. In 2020, a research focused on the use of games in Production Engineering courses resulted in the implementation of steps and methods in order to analyse the gains from the implementation of the games in the subjects. The research model adopted divides students into a control group and a test group, with the application of learning and perception assessments by the participants.

Keywords: Game-based learning; Production Engineering; Active Methodologies; Games.

1 Introduction

Brazilian education has undergone significant changes stimulated, mainly, by the implementation of the new National Curriculum Guidelines, which encourage the use of active methodologies in the teaching of engineering.

The updates proposed in the document seek to reduce the gap between university education and the needs of the market. According to Lázaro et al. (2018), active methodologies turn the student the most responsible for their learning, transforming it into the centerpiece of their training, which contributes to the development of significant competences: autonomy in learning, time management, prioritization of actions, decision making, among others.

Currently, dozens of types of active methodologies can be listed, among them: Project Based Learning, Problem Based Learning, Flipped Classroom, Team-Based Learning (TBL), Challenge Based Learning, Gamification, Game Based Learning (GBL).

Allied to this are the subjects of great value in academic education and which can be benefit from active methods of teaching and learning. In Production Engineering courses, Production Management subjects are perhaps the most important, presenting different theories and methods of management, which can be better understood through simulations and practical studies.

As it is not always possible to involve students in practical environments, through internships and partnerships with other institutions, teachers can use games and simulators, to improve the classes. This is because, according to Herrera et al. (2019), the complementation of traditional classes (Lecture) with GBL results in better learning, with greater student engagement, once that games stimulate learning, while making moments of interaction, simulation and reflection into relaxed and motivating experiences (Kishimoto, 2004; Machado et al., 1990; McDowell et al., 2006).

In addition to the motivational issue, games allow greater absorption of the content worked on, since they create valuable experiences and bring error as a source of learning (De Sousa & Salgado, 2015; Prado, 2018).

An example of this application is found in the Production Engineering course at a renowned Brazilian educational institution. The case in question, is aimed at Production Management III and IV, subjects whose main contents are: production planning, programming and control and the theory of restrictions and lean manufacturing, respectively,

For about 10 years, these subjects have been carried out with the support of different games: the "Beer Game" and the "Lean Board Game", in physical format and "Goldratt Simulator", a virtual simulator. But, although the teacher of the subjects understands the importance of using games to complement the class and understand the concepts covered, this application had not been the subject of research until the present moment.

However, in 2020, a research focused on the use of games in the Teaching of Production Engineering was initiated. With the research, there was a need to establish appropriate steps and methods capable of analyzing the gains from the implementation of the games in the course. Based on this research, a work model was proposed, which is presented in this article and is the main objective of this work.

2 Literature Review

The active methodologies are any educational approach in which students actively participate in the learning process, becoming the centerpiece of the process and the main responsible for their learning (Lázaro et al., 2018). They encourage debate and practice, as well as the revision of knowledge through explanation with other students, which, according to William Glasser's learning pyramid, results in higher levels of learning.

Measuring these learning gains has been a challenge for researchers who end up creating their own tools based on pedagogical theories and assessment models. Among the literature related to the use of games in the Teaching of Production Engineering, different theories, methodologies and tools are found, such as:

- **Bloom's taxonomy:** aims to assist in the identification and declaration of objectives related to cognitive development (Ferraz & Belhot, 2010). After updates, Bloom's Taxonomy is synthesized by the following categories: remember (knowledge), understand (understanding), apply (application), analyze (analysis), synthesize (synthesis) and create (evaluation).
- **Logic of input-process-outcome:** Fully aligned with the idea of transformation process, the logic of input, process and outcome is an excellent tool for the development, improvement and evaluation of games (Hense et al., 2009). Through this logic, developers and instructors are able to identify needs, objectives and plan the actions necessary for learning to be effective.
- **Keller Model or ARCS (Attention, Relevance, Confidence, Satisfaction) Model:** is a motivational design model that focus on elements that intended to ensure that the subjects worked are relevant and attractive and assist in the development of confidence and satisfaction of those involved (Kaneko et al, 2015).
- **Kirkpatrick model:** developed with the aim of analyzing and evaluating the results of training and education programs. It takes into account any style of training, both informal and formal, to determine the effectiveness of training based on four-level criteria: comprising reaction, learning, behaviour and results. The model must be implemented before, during and after training. The assessment must start at level one, progressing in the order of the levels (Smidt et al (2009).
- **Flow Theory:** developed by Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi in the 60s (Almeida & Budazy, 2019), the theory argues that there is a state (flow) in which a person is completely absorbed by a pleasant activity. In this state, in which the person does not even notice the time that passes, he is able to produce and achieve his best results, because mind and body are completely integrated and immersed in the moment. According to Yen and Lin (2020), the concept of flow has been widely applied to the context of sports, work, shopping, games, website use and computer use. In the context of game-based learning, the results of previous studies indicate that games help to place students in psychological states that increase their involvement in learning activities and focus on the tasks in question. According to Buil et al. (2018), Csikszentmihalyi's findings revealed that flow is achieved through a combination of skill and challenge.

In addition to these, other more specific approaches are found, such as: the SECI Model (Allal-Chérif et al., 2016), focused on knowledge management, "The Nine Gagne Events" (Mavromihales, 2019), which are steps towards a good instructional application, in line with mental learning conditions.

The approaches presented require planning, and must be supported by assessment tools, such as: questionnaires, forms and learning assessments. However, before establishing such tools, it is important to establish the group (s) that will be analyzed. The research can be carried out using:

- **Focus group:** These are useful groups for investigating complex behaviors that allow the researcher to interact with the participants. According to Krueger and Casey (2014 apud Almeida & Budazy, 2019), three elements are fundamental for the definition of a focus group: (i) number of participants: it must be between 2 (two) and 12 (twelve), at most; (ii) time limit: must be limited to two hours or less; and (iii) diversity: it must include people with characteristics common to the studied topic, with equal distribution of characteristics. Due to their quantitative limitations and strong interaction with the researcher, focus groups are used for qualitative analysis.
- **Control group and experimental group:** These are groups in which one of them is put in contact with the proposed experiment / treatment (experimental group) while the other is not undergoing intervention (control group). Experiments of this type are seen as controlled experiments, in which it is possible to test a hypothesis. For these groups, it is common to use post-experiment tests, comparing the results with each other.
- **Individual or several groups:** If it is impossible to carry out balanced and independent segmentations, it is possible to choose to carry out individual experiments and unify the applications by analyzing all the data in a grouped manner. When the control group is not established, it is common to perform pre- and post-tests, so that they can be analyzed and compared.

Regardless of the way established for the experiment, it is important that the data obtained are analyzed statistically, in order to verify the coherence of the answers (Cronbach's alpha), the interdependence of the variables (t tests) and the significance of the results (p-value).

Knowing what you want to measure is the first step in defining the experiment to be applied, as well as the assessment tools to be used. The main forms of evaluation the use of games are:

- **Perception assessments:** they help in the validation of games regarding their attractions (usability, entertainment) and attributes (learning potential). It is common for perception assessments to be based on flow theory, validating the immersion and engagement provided by the game (Khan & Pearce, 2015).
- **Self-assessments:** commonly performed in the pre and post-experiment model, self-assessments seek to identify changes in knowledge and behavior based on the participant's point of view. They are common assessments to be applied when behavior tends to change based on awareness, as when the subject is sustainability (Bascoul et al., 2013; Chappin et al., 2017; Cuesta & Nakano, 2017)
- **Learning assessments:** analyze the effectiveness of what has been learned. The tests can be performed from multiple choice questions, TRUE/FALSE and/or open/closed questions. The style of the questions is what will determine the level of evaluation, being able to stay only in the lower parts of Bloom's taxonomy (multiple choice questions) or transpose to the highest ones.

The assessments described can occur at different times, before (pre) and/or after (post) the experiment. However, according to All et al. (2017), pre-tests (assessments of learning before the experiment is carried out) do not seem to be an interesting tool, since they indicate what will be evaluated and, in this way, induce an intensification of studies in a more focused way.

3 Methodology

From a bibliographic research on the methods of validating the use of games in Production Engineering and related areas, it was possible to identify theories and assessment tools, which were analyzed, resulting in the proposal of a model for the application and evaluation of the use of games that could serve as a starting point for similar research.

In this way, this study is characterized as applied research, with a qualitative approach, with exploratory objectives, carried out through data collection through bibliographic and documentary research (Silva, 2001). Through the experiment it is also classified as a quantitative research, carried out to validate, not only the game, but also the proposed evaluation methodology.

A systematic research was applied, using in the following terms by Title, Summary and Keywords: ("educational game" OR "serious game" OR "game-based learning") AND ("production engineering" OR "industrial engineering" OR "manufacturing engineering" OR business OR logistic OR administration OR "supply chain" OR manufacture)

This research returned 419 published articles, in English and in Journal, which were evaluated, finding 15 significant experiments and diverse materials that reinforce the bibliographic review.

From these results it was possible to propose a structured model for the application and evaluation of the use of games, which has been used in the Production Management IV subject.

4 Development

Following theories, group formation and assessment tools, the proposed and developed model was divided into five stages:

1. **Definition of objectives (Figure 1):** From the subjects' teaching plan, the objectives of the experiments are identified through Bloom's Taxonomy;
2. **Design of the experiment (Figure 2):** Using the input - process - outcome model, the necessary components for the experiment are identified, the questionnaires elaborated and the whole process of application of the game is defined;
3. **Development of monitoring and validation models:** Based on the theories presented and the experiments observed, this study suggests to apply:
 - a. **a previous participant's characterization questionnaire (Figure 3):** in order to guarantee equivalence between the control and the experimental groups. This questionnaire should have characteristics such as: gender, age, level of previous knowledge about what will be addressed and the tool used. Following the defended by All et al. (2017), this first questionnaire should not ask conceptual questions;
 - b. **a perception questionnaire (Figure 4):** the perception / validation questionnaire of the game must be applied at the end of the experiment in order to identify the level of flow;
 - c. **a post-test (Figure 5):** to validate the learning, a TRUE/FALSE test should be applied to work on concepts, another multiple choice or even dissertative approach may compose the evaluation;
 - d. **a self-assessment questionnaire (Figure 6):** the self-assessment questionnaire should serve as a immediate feedback, based on statements that respond to the conceptual part of the post-test.
4. **Application of the activity and tools:** at this point, the classes plan is already adequate to carry out the different activities for the two groups.
5. **Analysis of results:** using statistical analysis, the following hypotheses are tested:
 - a. H1: the validation model is congruent (the results obtained between the tools are correlated)
 - b. H2: the use of the game allows for improvement in learning (evaluations of the experimental group are significantly better than those of the control group):

5 Results

To date, applied research has advanced the first three stages, being at the stage of applying the proposed model. Thus, the contribution of this study is the proposal and presentation of the models used by the three initial stages, detailed in the following items.

5.1 Definition of objectives

From the teaching plans of the subjects and Bloom's Taxonomy it is possible to identify the objectives of the game to be used and thus choose the most appropriate game / simulator. Thus, the first step proposes the analysis of the objectives of the subject according to Bloom's taxonomy for the definition of the best game/simulator to be used.

Production Management III – Objective: Analyse and create production planning and scheduling systems in companies		
Production Management IV - Objective: Understand the functioning and the importance of integrated management systems, with special attention to the production area.		
Cognitive domain categories	Production Management III	Production Management IV
1. Remember (knowledge)		
2. Understand (understanding)		X
3. Apply (application)		
4. Analyze (analysis)	X	
5. Synthesize (synthesis)	X	
6. Create (evaluation)		

Figure 1. Proposed objectives and their analyses by Bloom's Taxonomy.

Although Bloom's Taxonomy argues that the higher degrees must be preceded by the lower levels so that they can be well worked and absorbed, it is noted that, in this experiment, the subject of Production Management III brings comprehensive concepts, already worked by other subjects (Production Management I and II) and, therefore, there is a greater advance in the categories. In the sequence, the subject of Production Administration IV presents more defined concepts which translates into a need to add new knowledge and invest in its understanding. The proposed experiment, however, aims not only to understand these concepts, but also to apply them, since it allows them to be executed through simulation.

5.2 Design of the experiment

The input - process - outcome model helps to plan the needs and actions to develop the experiment.

INPUTS	PROCESS	OUTCOMES
Students: Age, gender, prior knowledge, motivations and expectations Game / simulator: Content and usability Teacher: Knowledge, motivation, expectation and preparation	Definition and division of working groups (experimental and control) Experiment application (in line with the ARCS model) Game feedback (decision results) User feedback (discussions and responses to questionnaires)	Acceptance: results of perception assessments Learning: results of post-test evaluations Validation: results of self-assessments and post-test assessments

Figure 2. Design of the experiment by the input - process - outcome model

5.3 Monitoring and validation models

Different tools were developed, based on the literature, as a way of proposing a consistent model, capable of obtaining qualitative and quantitative information for the initialization and analysis of the experiment.

5.2.1 Participant's characterization questionnaire

The participants' characterization questionnaire begins with the student's acceptance to participate in the experiment and is applied through "Google Forms". The questionnaire comprises the following questions:

Gender: () Female () Male () Not informed

Age: ____

What is your level of knowledge about Theory of Constraints (TOC)¹?

() I've never heard of it, I don't know what it is

() I've heard of it, but I don't know what it is

() I've heard of it and I know it's related to production systems

() I have read and / or attended classes on the subject

() I know and am able to discuss the matter properly

Based on the teaching plan presented for the subject, analyze the following statements using the Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree):

I believe that subject is important for my training

I would enroll in the course if it was not mandatory

I think the proposed assessment is fair

I think the proposed assessment is challenging

I think the proposed methodology looks interesting

¹ Main concept subject to be worked on in the experiment

Figure 3. Specific participant's characterization questionnaire

Such questionnaire must be applied at the beginning of the classes, before the first instructions on the content are offered, so that the groups can be properly organized.

5.3.1 Perception questionnaire

Perception analyzes reach the first two levels proposed by Kirkpatrick (reaction and learning). The first analysis will begin with the application of a perception questionnaire combined with the Flow Theory.

Using the Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), students from both groups should answer the following questions:

Absorption / Immersion:

1. During the activity I lost track of time
2. During the activity, I felt totally immersed
3. The activity made me excited
4. The activity made me feel self-confident
5. The activity stimulated my interest
6. The activity piqued my curiosity

Pleasure:

7. The activity gave me a good feeling

<p>8. I had fun during the activity</p> <p>9. The activity brought me joy</p> <p>10. The activity was pleasant</p> <p>Motivation:</p> <p>11. This type of activity should be carried out more frequently</p> <p>12. This is an activity that I willingly performed</p> <p>13. This is an activity that I would participate in even if it was not linked to the presence</p> <p>14. This is an activity that I would participate in even if it was not linked to the note</p> <p>15. This is an activity that I would do even though I didn't receive anything in return</p> <p>Skills:</p> <p>16. This activity improved my critical thinking</p> <p>17. This activity improved my problem-solving ability</p> <p>18. This activity improved my analytical ability</p> <p>19. This activity improved my ability to manage time and resources</p> <p>20. Some problems became clear with this activity</p>

Figure 4. A generic developed perception questionnaire

5.3.2 Post-test

After conducting the experiment, the following questionnaire must be applied to students in both groups. For a coherent evaluation it is fundamental that the questions are neutral, that is, they are not directly related to the game. We understand that the ideal would be the realization of conceptual questions that could be analyzed in a practical for example by a TRUE or FALSE model.

<p>Mark the sentences below with TRUE or FALSE:</p> <p>1. The theory of constraints (TOC) argues that companies have several restrictions that make it difficult to reach their goal</p> <p>2. The theory of constraints (TOC) states that great locations result in great globals</p> <p>3. Inactive capacity constrained resources (CCR) block the goal from being achieved</p> <p>4. Bottlenecks impede demands from being met</p> <p>5. Bottlenecks and CCRs are synonymous</p> <p>6. The buffer is the stock of materials in process that must exist throughout the production lines</p> <p>7. The rope is the production sequencing that is based on the drum</p> <p>8. The CCRs is the drum and it is from there that production must be planned</p> <p>9. An hour lost on a non-bottleneck resource is an hour lost on the entire system</p> <p>10. An hour saved on a non-bottleneck resource is an hour earned throughout the system</p>

Figure 5. The post-test with specific questions about Theory of Constraints

5.3.3 Self-assessment questionnaire

As a last tool, a self-assessment is suggested. In this, students will have the chance to review the contents worked and analyze their own level of understanding.

Analyze your level of understanding by checking 1 (I didn't understand) to 5 (I fully understood).

1. The theory of constraints (TOC) argues that companies have one or a few restrictions that make it difficult to reach their goal.
2. The theory of constraints (TOC) states that great locations do not necessarily result in great globals
3. Inactive Capacity Constrained Resources (CCR) will only block the goal from being reached if the adopted strategies turn it into a bottleneck (active CCR)
4. Bottlenecks impede demands from being met
5. Bottlenecks and CCRs are NOT synonymous. The CCR will only be a bottleneck when its capacity is or becomes less than necessary
6. The buffer is the stock of materials in process that must exist to ensure that the CCR (active or inactive) does not stop and for ensure that its production will be readily assembled and shipped
7. The rope is the production sequencing that is based on the drum
8. The CCR is the drum and it is from there that production must be planned
9. An hour lost on a NO bottleneck resource is NOT an hour lost on the entire system, but an hour lost on a bottleneck resource is an hour lost on the entire system.
10. An hour saved on a resource does NOT bottleneck it is NOT an hour earned across the system.

Figure 6. The self-assessment with specific affirmatives about Theory of Constraints

6 Conclusion

As a result of the Covid-19 pandemic, the classes schedules were changed, what postponed the beginning of the activities and therefore the experiment. Thus, it was not possible to finish the study and to present all the intended analyses on time.

However, it is clear that the proposal of a model of implementation and evaluation of the use of games for educational purposes becomes relevant, once there is the need to prove the effectiveness of tools and methodologies that complement the teaching-learning process.

This study presents a methodology that suggests the division of control and experimental groups in order to analyze the possible gains from the use of games and simulators. In order to carry out such an analysis, it is proposed to apply perception, learning and self-assessment questionnaires. Such questionnaires were designed to be simple to be answered and analyzed, based on different models found in the literature.

With the application of the following two steps, it will be possible to perform statistical analyses to verify the validity of the proposed model and the effectiveness of the use of the specific games (Beer Game and Lean Board Game) and simulator (Goldratt Simulator).

7 References

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